

Supplementary data

Experimental Section

DFT

All calculations were performed using spin-polarized density functional theory (DFT) as implemented in the Vienna ab initio simulation package (VASP).[1-3] The Perdew-Burke-Emzerhof (PBE) functional with a plane-wave cutoff energy of 500 eV was used. For structural optimizations, the Brillouin zone was sampled using a $5 \times 5 \times 1$ k-point grid based on the Monkhorst-Pack scheme, centered at Gamma. A vacuum space of 1.5 nm in the z direction (perpendicular to the basal plane) was used to avoid interactions between periodic images. The convergence criteria for the force on each atom was set to 0.02 eV/Å, while the electronic structure energy convergence criteria was 10^{-5} eV. The Grimme D3 method with Becke-Johnson parameters[4] were employed to account for Van der Waals interactions.[5] The vibrational modes were calculated at 298.15 K to obtain the zero-point energy, entropy, and temperature corrections to enthalpy.

The coupled proton-electron transfer (CPET) reactions were modelled using the computational hydrogen electrode (CHE) of Norskov.[6] In this approach, the voltage of reference (zero) is defined as for the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE), where gas-phase hydrogen is converted into protons and electrons (reversibly) at zero volts ($\text{H}^+ + \text{e}^- \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2$). Because this reaction is in equilibrium, one can make the approximation that the chemical potential of the proton-electron pair, $\mu(\text{H}^+) + \mu(\text{e}^-)$, equals half of the chemical potential of gas-phase H_2 , $1/2\mu(\text{H}_2)$. This last quantity can be trivially approximated via DFT calculations. As result, the chemical potential of the proton-electron pair can be adjusted based on the applied potential (U) with the equation (1):

$$\mu(\text{H}^+) + \mu(\text{e}^-) \rightarrow 1/2\mu(\text{H}_2) - eU \quad (1)$$

where e is the elementary positive charge. It is assumed that both proton and electron transfer occur in concert during an electrochemical step. For all of the electrochemical steps along the reaction path, the free energy change between intermediates was computed to indicate the feasibility of the electrochemical process, *i.e.*, no energy barriers were calculated. Based on the computational hydrogen electrode (CHE) model, the Gibbs free energy change (ΔG) was calculated using Equation (2):

$$\Delta G = \Delta E_{DFT} + \Delta E_{ZPE} - T\Delta S + kT \ln 10 \times pH - eU \quad (2)$$

where ΔE_{DFT} is the total energy from DFT simulations, ΔE_{ZPE} is the zero-point energy calculated from vibrational frequencies, T is the temperature (298.15 K), S is the entropy obtained from vibrational frequencies, k is the Boltzmann constant, and U is the electrode potential. Note that EZPE and S can be directly obtained from frequency calculations using VASPKIT.[7] We expect that the proton transfer from the solution to the adsorbates has low barriers, especially under negative potential.

Gas- or liquid-phase errors associated with H_2O , HNO_3 and NH_3 were corrected based on the method developed by Granda-Marulanda et al.[8] To avoid calculating the

charged molecule NO_3^- , the Gibbs free energy of aqueous NO_3^- was derived from those of gaseous HNO_3 and H_2 . Therefore, a correction for solvation (ΔG_{sol}) should be added to the $^*\text{NO}_3$ energy value, and it has been reported to be equal to 0.392 eV.[9]

$$\Delta G_{*NO_3}^{corr} = \Delta G_{*NO_3} + \Delta G_{sol} = \Delta G_{*NO_3} + 0.392 \text{ (3)}$$

Similarly, the adsorption energy for NO_3 has been computed considering the same correction:

$$\Delta G_{*NO_3}^{abs} = G_{*NO_3} - G_* - G_{HNO_3} + \frac{1}{2}G_{H_2} + 0.392 \text{ (4)}$$

The d band center (ϵ_d) for the metal atom involved in the catalysis around the adsorption sites is given by

$$\epsilon_d = \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \rho(E)(E-E_F) dE}{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (E-E_F) dE} \text{ (5)}$$

where $\rho(E)$ is the density of state (DOS) projected on the d-states of the metal atoms and E_F is the Fermi energy of the system. Bader charge analysis was considered to quantify the charge transfer of selected intermediates.

Product quantification

The evolving gases were analyzed with an Agilent 490 Micro GC system (Molsieve 5 Å column using Ar as carrier gas). N-containing species were detected by colorimetry with ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectrophotometer. In particular, NH_3 was also quantified by the solution ^1H NMR spectroscopy method. In detail, 400 μL of electrolyte and 100 μL of 1M H_2SO_4 were mixed with 100 μL deuterium oxide containing a known concentration DMSO as the internal standard.

Determination of ammonia

The concentration of produced ammonia was spectrophotometrically detected by the Nessler's reagent method. Due to the large concentration of ammonia, the electrolyte after 1 h of electrolysis was diluted by 20-50 times to reach the detected range. Then, 5 mL of the diluted electrolyte, 0.2 mL of a 1 M NaOH solution with 5% salicylic acid and 5% sodium citrate, 0.5 mL of 0.05 M NaClO and 0.2 mL of 1% sodium nitroferrocyanide (III) dihydrate ($\text{C}_5\text{FeN}_6\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) solution were mixed. After standing in the dark for 3 h, the concentration of indophenol blue was detected by an ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 635 nm in the absorption spectrum.

Determination of NO_2^-

The Griess test was adopted to evaluate the concentration NO_2^- in electrolyte. Firstly, the Griess reagents were prepared by adding 0.1 g N-(1-naphthyl)-ethylenediamine dihydrochloride, 1.0 g sulfonamide and 2.94 mL H_3PO_4 in 50 mL deionized water. 5 mL electrolyte after diluting by adding deionized water, and then 0.1 mL chromogenic agent was added. After standing for 20 minutes, the absorbance curve was measured in the wavelength range of 400-700 nm and the absorbance value of 540 nm was selected. A series of NaNO_2 solutions with different concentrations were used to determine the

standard curve.

Determination of N₂H₄

Hydrazine in the electrolytes was detected by the Watt-Chrisp method. A mixture of ethanol (100 mL), para(dimethylamino) benzaldehyde (2.0 g) and HCl (concentrated, 12 mL) were used as a color reagent. 2 mL color reagent was added into 2 mL of diluted electrolyte. After 30 min, the absorbance was measured at a wavelength of 458 nm. The standard hydrazine monohydrate solutions with the given concentrations of hydrazine in 0.2 M K₂SO₄ were also prepared for building the calibration curves.

SUPPORTING FIGURES AND TABLES

Fig. S1 XRD patterns of (a) FC/CB and FC, and (b) MC/CB and MC.

Fig. S2. TEM image of FMC.

Fig. S3. SEM images of FMC (a-c) and FMC/CB (d-f) at different magnifications.

Fig. S4. (a) TEM image of MC/CB and corresponding nanoparticle size distribution histogram; (b) high resolution TEM image of MC/CB and its lattice fringes.

Fig. S5 (a) TEM image of FC/CB and corresponding nanoparticle size distribution histogram; (b) high resolution TEM image of FC/CB and its lattice fringes.

Fig. S6. Elemental mapping of FMC/CB.

Fig. S7. Experimental XPS Fe 2p peak of FMC/CB and FC/CB.

Fig. S8. The EXAFS fitting curves of FMC at R space.

Fig. S9 The EXAFS fitting curves of FMC at k space.

Fig. S10 The electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) of different samples based on the double-layer capacitance.

Fig. S11. (a) UV-Vis absorption spectra of the NH₃ standard solution at different concentrations. (b) Linear relationship between the light absorbance at 635 nm and the concentration of NH₃ standard solution.

Fig. S12. (a) UV-Vis absorption spectra of the NO_2^- standard solution at different concentrations. (b) Linear relationship between the light absorbance at 540 nm and the concentration of NO_2^- standard solution.

Fig. S13 A representative ^1H NMR spectrum for NH_3 quantification recorded using water suppression mode.

Fig. S14. NO₃RR performance at different NO₃⁻ concentration.

Fig. S15. (a) Chronoamperometry in FMC/CB at -0.3 V vs. RHE for 24 h indicating NH₃ FE (orange triangles) calculated at different times. (b) Linear sweep voltammetry of the FMC/CB electrode prior and after the 24 h chronoamperometry.

Fig. S16. XRD patterns of FMC/CB prior and after -0.3 V vs. RHE applied bias for 24 h.

Fig. S17. Reaction pathways for MC (a) FMC (b) and FC (c) interfaces at different applied potentials of 0 and -0.33 V. The intermediate structures adsorbed on the surfaces are depicted in the insets. Colour code: red-oxygen, blue- nitrogen, white-hydrogen, yellow-iron, purple-molybdenum and brown-carbon.

The β - Mo_2C hexagonal P63/mmc unit cell was considered as starting geometry for the generation of the $3 \times 3 \times 1$ supercell for the interface, with two layers considered for the interface. According to literature, the (101) plane is the most exposed in experiment, thus it was selected for the computations. The Mo_2C model has been derived from the Material Project database. The same supercell has been used for the Fe-doped interface.

The electrochemical reaction consists of a series of deoxidation reactions, $*NO_3^- \rightarrow *NO_2 \rightarrow *NO \rightarrow *N$, followed by hydrogenation reactions, $*N \rightarrow *NH \rightarrow *NH_2 \rightarrow *NH_3$.

Accordingly, we consider the central atom of the cell as the catalytic center for both Mo_2C and Fe-doped surfaces. For all intermediates, the most stable adsorption configuration with the lowest total energies were employed to illustrate the NO₃RR pathway, and to assess the activities of the different surfaces. According to the experimental conditions, pH=13 and overpotential of -0.33 V were considered, within the computational hydrogen electrode method.

Table S1. Weight percentage of Fe and Mo in different samples determined by ICP-OES analysis.

Samples	Fe wt%	Mo wt%
FMC	8.65	37.19
FMC/CB	2.60	22.17
FC/CB	10.71	0
MC/CB	0	23.44
FMC/CB solvent	4.61	0.01

Table S2. EXAFS fitting parameters at the Fe K-edge for various samples. N: coordination numbers; R: bond distance; σ^2 : Debye-Waller factors; ΔE_0 : the inner potential correction; R factor: goodness of fit.

Sample	Path	N	R (Å)	σ^2 (10^{-3}Å^2)	ΔE_0 (eV)	R-factor
FMC	Fe-C	3.0±0.4	2.06±0.01	4.7±0.6	1.3±1.0	0.001
	Fe-Fe	2.4±0.6	2.52±0.02	3.0±0.8	6.7±1.2	
	Fe-Mo	0.7±0.3	2.84±0.03			
FMCCB	Fe-C	6.4±0.6	2.05±0.01	8.3±0.5	-4.5±0.6	0.004
	Fe-Mo	2.7±0.6	2.96±0.02	8.6±1.0	-1.7±1.0	

Table S3. The comparison of the FMC/CB electrocatalytic NO₃RR performance with those of reported electrocatalysts.

No.	Catalysts	Electrolyte	Potential (V vs. RHE)	NH ₃ yield	FE NH ₃ (%)
1	FeMoC/CB	0.1 M KOH and 0.1 M KNO ₃	-0.3V	14.66 mg/h/cm ²	94.35%
			-0.4V	19.15 mg/h/cm ²	91.47%
			-0.5V	26.71 mg/h/cm ²	87.95%

2[10]	3.8 wt % Ru ₁ /Mo ₂ C	1 M KOH and 0.1 M KNO ₃	-0.2V	25.1 mg/h/cm ²	80%
3[11]	Mo ₂ C/RGO	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄ + 0.1 M NO ₃ ⁻	-0.6V	4.8 mg/h/cm ²	85.20%
4[12]	Fe/Ni ₂ P on carbon cloth	0.2 M K ₂ SO ₄ + 0.05 M NO ₃ ⁻	-0.4V	4.16 mg/h/cm ²	94.30%
5[13]	Fe ₃ O ₄ /SS	0.1 M NaOH + 0.1 M NO ₃ ⁻	-0.5V	10.15 mg/h/cm ²	91.50%
6[14]	Fe SAC on glassy carbon	0.1 M K ₂ SO ₄ + 0.5 M NO ₃ ⁻	-0.66V	~1.95 mg/h/cm ²	75%
7[15]	CoO _x Nanosheets	0.1 M KOH + 0.1 M NO ₃ ⁻	-0.3V	82.4 mg/h/mg _{cat.}	93%
8[16]	Co ₃ O ₄ @NiO	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄ + 200ppm NO ₃ ⁻	-0.7V	0.0069 mmol/h/mg _{cat.}	55%
9[17]	NiCo ₂ O ₄ /CC	0.1 M NaOH + 0.1 M NO ₃ ⁻	-0.6V	0.97 mmol/h/cm ²	95%
10[18]	Ru-CuNW on Cu foam	1 M KOH + 0.32 M NO ₃ ⁻	0.04V	76.89 mg/h/cm ²	96%
11[19]	Pd/TiO ₂ on carbon cloth	1 M LiCl + 0.25 M NO ₃ ⁻	-0.7V	1.12 mg/h/cm ²	92.10%
12[20]	Strained Ru nanoclusters on carbon paper	1 M KOH + 1 M NO ₃ ⁻	-0.2V	19.89 mg/h/cm ²	~100%

Table S4. Energetic contributions (total energy, zero-point energy and entropy) to the Gibbs free energy for all the intermediates on MC. All values are reported in eV. The temperature has been considered at 298K.

Intermediate	Etot	ZPE	TS	Gibbs free energy
* (bare Mo ₂ C surface)	-302.165	0.615	0.493	-301.755
*NO ₃	-328.668	1.040	0.732	-327.960
*NO ₃ H	-331.481	1.312	0.731	-330.496
*NO ₂	-323.197	0.926	0.633	-322.541
*NO ₂ H	-325.848	1.162	0.751	-325.027
*NO	-316.820	0.829	0.639	-316.280
*NOH	-319.661	1.087	0.661	-318.876
*HNO	-319.823	1.101	0.600	-318.980
*NHOH	-323.482	1.372	0.678	-322.803
*N	-310.175	0.716	0.552	-309.696

*NH	-314.231	0.979	0.586	-313.503
*NH ₂	-318.384	1.287	0.609	-317.354
*NH ₃	-323.125	1.667	0.630	-321.734

Table S5. Energetic contributions (total energy, zero-point energy and entropy) to the Gibbs free energy for all the intermediates on FMC. All values are reported in eV. The temperature has been considered at 298K.

Intermediate	Etot	ZPE	TS	Gibbs free energy
* (bare Fe-Mo ₂ C surface)	-298.347	0.589	0.518	-297.979
*NO ₃	-324.380	0.992	0.796	-323.763
*NO ₃ H	-327.438	1.292	0.783	-326.510
*NO ₂	-318.660	0.873	0.707	-318.104
*NO	-312.302	0.787	0.704	-311.846
*NOH	-314.984	1.067	0.685	-314.227
*HNO	-315.620	1.091	0.620	-314.802
*NHOH	-319.238	1.384	0.693	-318.546
*N	-304.709	0.683	0.592	-304.287
*NH	-308.676	0.916	0.642	-308.047
*NH ₂	-313.722	1.234	0.628	-312.763
*NH ₃	-318.618	1.630	0.661	-317.282

Table S6. Energetic contributions (total energy, zero-point energy and entropy) to the Gibbs free energy for all the intermediates on FC. All values are reported in eV. The temperature has been considered at 298K.

Intermediate	Etot	ZPE	TS	Gibbs free energy
* (bare FeC surface)	-240.706	0.536	0.332	-240.298
*NO ₃	-268.372	0.998	0.744	-267.712
*NO ₃ H	-269.716	1.294	0.751	-268.765
*NO ₂	-260.478	0.881	0.662	-259.883
*NO ₂ H	-263.865	1.186	0.695	-262.994
*NO	-254.686	0.814	0.645	-254.165
*NOH	-257.118	1.080	0.657	-256.332
*HNO	-257.870	1.086	0.628	-257.065
*N	-246.902	0.701	0.549	-246.434
*NH	-250.887	0.930	0.609	-250.225
*NH ₂	-256.074	1.258	0.614	-255.077
*NH ₃	-261.101	1.637	0.645	-259.749

References.

- [1] P.E. Blöchl, Projector augmented-wave method, *Physical review B*, 50 (1994) 17953.
- [2] G. Kresse, J. Furthmüller, Efficient iterative schemes for ab initio total-energy calculations using a plane-wave basis set, *Physical review B*, 54 (1996) 11169.
- [3] G. Kresse, J. Furthmüller, Efficiency of ab-initio total energy calculations for metals and semiconductors using a plane-wave basis set, *Computational materials science*, 6 (1996) 15-50.
- [4] S. Grimme, S. Ehrlich, L. Goerigk, Effect of the damping function in dispersion corrected density functional theory, *Journal of computational chemistry*, 32 (2011) 1456-1465.
- [5] S. Grimme, J. Antony, S. Ehrlich, H. Krieg, A consistent and accurate ab initio parametrization of density functional dispersion correction (DFT-D) for the 94 elements H-Pu, *The Journal of chemical physics*, 132 (2010).
- [6] J.K. Nørskov, J. Rossmeisl, A. Logadottir, L. Lindqvist, J.R. Kitchin, T. Bligaard, H. Jonsson, Origin of the overpotential for oxygen reduction at a fuel-cell cathode, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 108 (2004) 17886-17892.
- [7] V. Wang, N. Xu, J.-C. Liu, G. Tang, W.-T. Geng, VASPKIT: A user-friendly interface facilitating high-throughput computing and analysis using VASP code, *Computer Physics Communications*, 267 (2021) 108033.
- [8] L.P. Granda-Marulanda, A. Rendon-Calle, S. Builes, F. Illas, M.T. Koper, F. Calle-Vallejo, A semiempirical method to detect and correct DFT-based gas-phase errors and its application in electrocatalysis, *Acs Catalysis*, 10 (2020) 6900-6907.
- [9] F. Calle-Vallejo, M. Huang, J.B. Henry, M.T. Koper, A.S. Bandarenka, Theoretical design and experimental implementation of Ag/Au electrodes for the electrochemical reduction of nitrate, *Physical chemistry chemical physics*, 15 (2013) 3196-3202.
- [10] O. Peng, Q. Hu, X. Zhou, R. Zhang, Y. Du, M. Li, L. Ma, S. Xi, W. Fu, Z.-X. Xu, Swinging hydrogen evolution to nitrate reduction activity in molybdenum carbide by ruthenium doping, *ACS Catalysis*, 12 (2022) 15045-15055.
- [11] X. Li, S. Wang, G. Wang, P. Shen, D. Ma, K. Chu, Mo₂C for electrocatalytic nitrate reduction to ammonia, *Dalton Transactions*, 51 (2022) 17547-17552.
- [12] R. Zhang, Y. Guo, S. Zhang, D. Chen, Y. Zhao, Z. Huang, L. Ma, P. Li, Q. Yang, G. Liang, Efficient Ammonia Electrosynthesis and Energy Conversion through a Zn-Nitrate Battery by Iron Doping Engineered Nickel Phosphide Catalyst, *Advanced Energy Materials*, 12 (2022) 2103872.
- [13] X. Fan, L. Xie, J. Liang, Y. Ren, L. Zhang, L. Yue, T. Li, Y. Luo, N. Li, B. Tang, In situ grown Fe₃O₄ particle on stainless steel: A highly efficient electrocatalyst for nitrate reduction to ammonia, *Nano Research*, (2022) 1-6.
- [14] Z.-Y. Wu, M. Karamad, X. Yong, Q. Huang, D.A. Cullen, P. Zhu, C. Xia, Q. Xiao, M. Shakouri, F.-Y. Chen, Electrochemical ammonia synthesis via nitrate reduction on Fe single atom catalyst, *Nature communications*, 12 (2021) 2870.
- [15] J. Wang, C. Cai, Y. Wang, X. Yang, D. Wu, Y. Zhu, M. Li, M. Gu, M. Shao, Electrocatalytic reduction of nitrate to ammonia on low-cost ultrathin CoO_x nanosheets, *ACS Catalysis*, 11 (2021) 15135-15140.

- [16] Y. Wang, C. Liu, B. Zhang, Y. Yu, Self-template synthesis of hierarchically structured Co₃O₄@ NiO bifunctional electrodes for selective nitrate reduction and tetrahydroisoquinolines semi-dehydrogenation, *Sci. China Mater*, 63 (2020) 2530-2538.
- [17] Q. Liu, L. Xie, J. Liang, Y. Ren, Y. Wang, L. Zhang, L. Yue, T. Li, Y. Luo, N. Li, Ambient ammonia synthesis via electrochemical reduction of nitrate enabled by NiCo₂O₄ nanowire array, *Small*, 18 (2022) 2106961.
- [18] F.-Y. Chen, Z.-Y. Wu, S. Gupta, D.J. Rivera, S.V. Lamberts, S. Pecaut, J.Y.T. Kim, P. Zhu, Y.Z. Finfrock, D.M. Meira, Efficient conversion of low-concentration nitrate sources into ammonia on a Ru-dispersed Cu nanowire electrocatalyst, *Nature nanotechnology*, 17 (2022) 759-767.
- [19] Y. Guo, R. Zhang, S. Zhang, Y. Zhao, Q. Yang, Z. Huang, B. Dong, C. Zhi, Pd doping-weakened intermediate adsorption to promote electrocatalytic nitrate reduction on TiO₂ nanoarrays for ammonia production and energy supply with zinc–nitrate batteries, *Energy & Environmental Science*, 14 (2021) 3938-3944.
- [20] J. Li, G. Zhan, J. Yang, F. Quan, C. Mao, Y. Liu, B. Wang, F. Lei, L. Li, A.W. Chan, Efficient ammonia electrosynthesis from nitrate on strained ruthenium nanoclusters, *Journal of the american chemical society*, 142 (2020) 7036-7046.